

Cognitive Science

Isbell Conjugacy for Developing Cognitive Science

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>What is cognition? Equivalently, what is cognition good for? Or, what is it that would not be but for human cognition? But for human cognition, there would not be science. Based on this kinship between individual cognition and collective science, here we put forward Isbell conjugacy--the adjointness between objective geometry and subjective algebra--as a scientific method for developing cognitive science. We begin with the correspondence between categorical perception and category theory. Next, we show how the Gestalt maxim is subsumed by the mathematical construct of colimit, a generalization of summation. The universal mapping property definitions of mathematical constructs, by virtue of being the best with respect to the universe of discourse, can be learned using reinforcement learning algorithms, which raises the possibility of abstracting the architecture of mathematics by artificial intelligence. Subsequently, we present naturality (to be contrasted with miracles), understood as 'Becoming consistent with Being', which governs the transformations of both things and their theories, as the zeroth law of change. Furthermore, the contrast--physical [mechanism] vs. biological [organism]--is smoothed via natural transformation, wherein transformations are respectful of the cohesion of the objects transformed. In closing, upon recognizing the scientific value of learning difficult-to-master differential calculus by physicists, of learning a strange four-letter language by biologists, and of learning the grammar of our respective mother tongues, we make a case for learning the theory of naturality/category theory for developing cognitive science.</p>

To,

Professor Rick Dale

Executive Editor

Cognitive Science

Dear Professor Dale,

I am herewith submitting our Letter, coauthored with Professor Sisir Roy, and entitled 'Isbell Conjugacy for Developing Cognitive Science' to be considered for publication as a 'Letter to the Editorial Board' in your journal: Cognitive Science. Our submission is in response to your call: CfL: "Progress and Puzzles of Cognitive Science".

Our Letter was motivated by a profound progress in cognitive science understood as the science of knowing. First, let us recall the main objective of cognitive science: How do we know? Recognizing the limitations of the Fregean definition of CONCEPT as a SET of properties (or features), the definition of CONCEPT was refined into a CATEGORY, with properties and their mutual determinations as objects and morphisms, respectively (of the category). Notwithstanding the realization that concepts is where cognitive science went wrong, this category theoretic advance in our understanding of how we go from particulars to generals (theory and models) has been largely ignored, presumably under the pretext: mathematical knowing is too special to inform knowing in general. However, reflecting on the development of

science readily brings to mind that it is the too special motion of dropped objects that led to the development of the science of motion.

The kinship between mathematics (in particular and science in general) and cognition has been brought into clear focus by way of spelling out how 'representation', figuring in the foundational tenet of cognitive science: "cognition is computation of representations" (Nat. Hum. Behav. 3, 782, 2019), is calculated ([Mind & Matter 15, 161-184, 2017](#)). Representation (or model), according to functorial semantics, is a contravariant functor interpreting a theory (into a background category, with the theory abstracted from the given category of particulars; [Reprints in Theory and Applications of Categories 5, 8-12, 2004](#)).

Returning to the main objective of cognitive science--how we know--we find that how we know depends on what we are trying to know, i.e. ontology determines epistemology (cf. sense organs along with telescope for distant objects vs. microscope for tiny objects). As such cognitive science can develop only as a complex: ontology vis-à-vis epistemology. Comparing ontology and epistemology to geometry and algebra, respectively, in our Letter, we introduce Isbell conjugacy--the adjointness between geometry and algebra--as a method to develop cognitive science.

We discuss these mathematical insights into knowing in a manner readily accessible to the multidisciplinary audience of your journal. In closing, our Letter brings out the reach of Isbell conjugacy between objective geometry and its subjective reflections in algebra into focus so as to facilitate ready recognition of the relevance of Isbell conjugacy for the development of cognitive science.

If I may, the following may be considered for reviewing our Letter since they are experts in both cognitive science and category theory.

Professor Michael A. Arbib (arbib@usc.edu)

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Professor Valeria Giardino (Valeria.Giardino@ens.fr)

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We'd also like to request the following members of your esteemed Editorial Board to be our Letter's Handling Editors.

Professor Kinga Morsanyi

Professor Iris van Rooij

Professor Rick Dale

Professor Dr. Max Louwerse

We earnestly hope that you will find our Letter suitable for publication in your journal Cognitive Science. We sincerely thank you for your kind consideration of our Letter and we eagerly look forward to hearing from you.

Thanking you,

Yours truly,

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17 **Conflicts of interests:** None

1 **Title:** Isbell Conjugacy for Developing Cognitive Science

2

3 **Abstract**

4 What is cognition? Equivalently, what is cognition good for? Or, what is it that would not be
5 but for human cognition? But for human cognition, there would not be science. Based on this
6 kinship between individual cognition and collective science, here we put forward Isbell
7 conjugacy--the adjointness between objective geometry and subjective algebra--as a scientific
8 method for developing cognitive science. We begin with the correspondence between
9 categorical perception and category theory. Next, we show how the Gestalt maxim is subsumed
10 by the mathematical construct of colimit, a generalization of summation. The universal mapping
11 property definitions of mathematical constructs, by virtue of being the best with respect to the
12 universe of discourse, can be learned using reinforcement learning algorithms, which raises the
13 possibility of abstracting the architecture of mathematics by artificial intelligence. Subsequently,
14 we present naturality (to be contrasted with miracles), understood as 'Becoming consistent with
15 Being', which governs the transformations of both things and their theories, as the zeroth law of
16 change. Furthermore, the contrast--physical [mechanism] vs. biological [organism]--is smoothed
17 via natural transformation, wherein transformations are respectful of the cohesion of the objects
18 transformed. In closing, upon recognizing the scientific value of learning difficult-to-master
19 differential calculus by physicists, of learning a strange four-letter language by biologists, and of
20 learning the grammar of our respective mother tongues, we make a case for learning the theory
21 of naturality/category theory for developing cognitive science.

22 1. Categories and Naturality

23

24 The most advanced scientific method for defining objects and operations is in terms of 'what
25 they are good for' (Lawvere & Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 26-29), which is a refinement of functional
26 definitions. Human cognition is good for developing science. Not surprisingly, individual
27 cognition and collective science have much in common: cognition is science writ small (see
28 Einstein, 1936, p. 349; Fodor, 2006, p. 93; Schapira, 2016). Based on this propinquity
29 (Ehresmann & Vanbremeersch, 2007, p. 12; Lawvere, 1994; Posina, Ghista, & Roy, 2017), here
30 we show how to develop cognitive science.

31 Our conscious experiences are categorical (Albright, 2013); so is mathematics (Lawvere, 1972,
32 p. 10; Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009). But, what exactly is meant by 'categorical'? The cat that I
33 see sitting on the wall across my window partakes in the essence--catness--that is characteristic
34 of the category of cats. The essence--catness--specifies the way in which parts (eyes, whiskers,
35 nose, mouth, tail, etc.) of a whole (cat) stick together. Equally importantly, this essence is
36 preserved as one object of a category is transformed into another object of the category (e.g.
37 catness is preserved in the transformation: playful cat --> watchful cat). Not unlike objects of
38 different categories--textbook, chair, and table--populating our perceptual experience,
39 mathematics also consists of various categories such as sets, dynamical systems, functions, and
40 graphs (ibid. pp. 11-21, 133-151). The abstract essence/theory of a category of objects is
41 adequate for completely characterizing every object of the category and to tell apart any two
42 transformations of objects (Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, pp. 23, 177-181, 213-215, 245-250).

43 The Gestalt maxim--the whole is different from the sum of its parts--figures prominently in
44 cognitive neuroscience (Albright et al., 2000). In order to see the 'difference' that the Gestalt
45 maxim highlights, we ask: what does it mean to say 'a whole is the sum of its parts' (e.g. $\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{2} =$
46 $\mathbf{3}$, where $\mathbf{1} = \{*\}$, $\mathbf{2} = \{*, *\}$, $\mathbf{3} = \{*, *, *\}$)? A whole ($\mathbf{3}$) is the sum of its parts ($\mathbf{1}$ and $\mathbf{2}$), if what
47 every part does determines what the whole does. Just as in the case of concepts, where
48 constituent features can be related to one another (Smith & Medin, 1981, p. 83), the summands
49 can also be related (say, a function between $\mathbf{1}$ and $\mathbf{2}$). Colimit, a generalization of sum, takes into
50 account [any] morphisms relating objects, and, as such, spells out the "different" in the Gestalt
51 maxim. The mathematical construct of colimit has been brought to bear on cognitive science
52 (Ehresmann & Vanbremeersch, 2007, 2019). The aforementioned mathematical definition of
53 sum as a whole that is determined by its parts is a universal mapping property definition, wherein
54 the sum ($\mathbf{3}$) is unique with respect to the summands ($\mathbf{1}$ and $\mathbf{2}$). The universal mapping property
55 definition of mathematical objects and operations, by virtue of being the best in the given
56 universe of discourse, can be abstracted using reinforcement learning algorithms (Posina, 2022a),
57 which, in turn, raises the possibility of abstracting the architecture of mathematics by artificial
58 intelligence.

59 Comparing the apparently incongruent physical mechanism vs. biological organism with
60 change vs. unity, we find that the mechanistic transformations underlying the growth and
61 development of a biological organism are respectful of the cohesion of the organism (e.g. aging
62 did not tear me apart). This 'Becoming consistent with Being' (Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, p.
63 152) or 'naturality' is what called for the abstraction of category theory from the mathematical
64 practice (Eilenberg & MacLane, 1945; see also Lawvere, 2017, p. 12). Given that every
65 morphism transforming one object into another of a category is respectful of the structural

66 essence of the category (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 210), we now put forward 'Becoming
67 consistent with Being' or, equivalently, 'all changes are natural' (with Set-valued contravariant
68 functors as objects; Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, p. 378; see also Posina, 2022b) as the zeroth law
69 of motion. This scientifically advanced understanding of 'natural' subsumes not only physical,
70 biological, and cognitive sciences, but also cultural, political, and social sciences (cf. societies do
71 not change willy-nilly; see Lawvere, 1999; Posina, 2020). Also note that not only are the
72 transformations of things natural, but also that of their theories, all of which asserts that science--
73 understood as a reflective part of reality (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 84-85; see also
74 Clementino & Picado, 2008, p. 6)--is not a miracle machine (cf. Sarewitz, 2017). In accordance
75 with commonsense, miracles (and prophetic revelations) are unnatural.

76

77

78 **2. Compounding Epistemology and Ontology**

79

80 The most basic question of cognitive science is: How do we know? How we know depends,
81 not surprisingly, on what we are trying to know (cf. sense organs along with a telescope for
82 distant objects vs. microscope for tiny objects). One immediate implication of the just stated
83 realization is that the development of cognitive science can only take place as a complex:
84 epistemology vis-à-vis ontology. Inspired by eminently useful analogies such as the Bohr atom,
85 here we put forward Isbell conjugacy (Lawvere, 2005, pp. 16-20; 2016, pp. 1-3; see also
86 Lawvere & Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 171-176) as a method to compound epistemology and ontology
87 into which reality is resolved.

88 What is Isbell conjugacy? How does it help in the much-desired maturation of cognitive
89 science? In comparing algebra and geometry to epistemology and ontology, respectively, we
90 find that Isbell conjugacy, which spells out the adjointness between subjective algebra and
91 objective geometry, can inform the synthesis of epistemology and ontology into which reality is
92 analyzed (see appendix A4 in Posina, Ghista, & Roy, 2017 for an accessible discussion of
93 adjointness). In doing so, Isbell conjugacy constitutes the scientific foundation solid enough to
94 build cognitive science.

95 To facilitate the scientific program of bringing Isbell conjugacy to bear on cognitive science,
96 we begin with a familiar mathematical construct: function. A function $f: A \rightarrow B$, geometrically
97 speaking, is an A-shaped figure in B; the very same function $f: A \rightarrow B$, algebraically, is a B-
98 valued property of A (Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, pp. 81-85, 370-371). As an illustration of
99 resourcefulness of the aforementioned function, we note that implicit in it--in the function
100 mapping elements to elements--is the most basic principle of Becoming (or change) consistent
101 with Being (unity) or naturality (see Exercise 7.22a in Lawvere & Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 135). But
102 for the naturality, science would not be possible (e.g. reconstruction of objects from observed
103 changes, as in characterizing the receptive field of a neuron from observed changes in firing rate
104 in response to stimulus changes; see Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, pp. 360-361 for the
105 mathematics of reconstruction as a category of right actions of a monoid objectifying given
106 changes).

107 Summing it all, since reality consists, as noted above, of parts--individual cognition and
108 collective science--reflective of the reality, we need a mathematical category of Reflecting in
109 addition to the categories of Being and Becoming in order to bridge the two categories of
110 objective reality on the one hand and its subjective reflections on the other. The mathematical

- 111 category of Reflecting, with conjugate adjoints dualizing subjective algebra into objective
112 geometry as objects, makes room for the basis of science--human cognition--in the scientific
113 representation of reality.

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Action Letter on Cognitive Science Submission 22-294

1 message

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22-294
"Isbell Conjugacy for Developing Cognitive Science"
Venkata Rayudu Posina; Sisir Roy

Cognitive Science

Dear rayudu,

Thank you for your submission to *Cognitive Science*. After conducting a preliminary review, I regret to inform you that I have decided that we are unable to consider your manuscript for publication in the journal.

The journal receives many more submissions than we can consider for publication, and therefore a significant percentage of articles are not sent to outside reviewers after a preliminary review by the Editors. The primary reason for this is determining which submissions have the strongest fit with the journal's aims to publish high quality research of wide multidisciplinary relevance. Our decision regarding your submission is therefore not necessarily a reflection of the quality of your work, but rather the constraints that we face in publishing articles that fit the journal's aims most clearly.

This idea of extending Isbell conjugacy seems very intriguing and provocatively general -- unfortunately, to best develop this framework, a more expanded paper would be required. I appreciate this submission to our special initiative of "Progress & Puzzles," but the focused nature of your letter on such a new idea would seem to be most comprehensible under a more expanded theoretical or review paper -- and even then, this theoretical proposal itself may also be best suited to a topical journal, such as a journal in philosophy of mind or applied logic.

We are sorry to bring this disappointing news, but we do hope that you will consider *Cognitive Science* for future submissions.

While we were unable to consider your submission for publication at this time, Wiley is committed to helping researchers find the right home for their work. This journal participates in Wiley's Transfer Desk Assistant service, which helps suggest a suitable new journal and simplifies resubmission, saving you the time and effort of starting your submission over. Wiley's Transfer Desk will now identify relevant publications that would be an appropriate match for your manuscript. If there are matches, you will shortly receive recommendations in a direct communication from the Wiley Transfer Desk.

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Yours sincerely,

Rick Dale

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